

A Novel Technique of Black Tea Quality Prediction Using Electronic Tongue Signals

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Abstract— Electronic tongue (ET) system is under extensive development for automatic analysis and prediction of quality of different industrial end products. Each sensor in an electronic tongue system generates a specific electronic response in presence of different organic or inorganic compounds in the sample. The vital part of the ET system is the discrimination of the complex pattern generated by the sensor array. In this work, a novel technique of black tea quality estimation is presented using the ET signals. A moving window is used to extract discrete wavelet transform coefficients from the transient response of ET. The energy in different frequency bands are used as the features of the ET signal for different positions of the window. The prediction of a new sample is performed by the highest score obtained by a particular class by testing all the patterns generated by windowing ET signal. The performance of the proposed technique is verified to estimate black tea quality using two kernel classifiers, namely support vector machine (SVM) and recently proposed vector valued regularized kernel function approximation (VVRKFA) method. High prediction accuracy of both the classifiers confirms the effectiveness of the proposed technique of tea quality estimation using ET signals.

Index Terms— E-tongue, feature extraction, kernel classifiers, support vector machine (SVM), VVRKFA, wavelet features.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE electronic tongue (ET), also known as artificial tongue, is proficient in discriminating between substances with different taste modalities as well as distinguishing different substances eliciting same taste [1], [2], [3]. There are several sensors forming arrays in an ET system alike the human receptors those are responsible for sensing taste. The information given by each sensor is complementary and the amalgamations of different sensors consequences generate a unique pattern. The multi-sensor array system of electronic tongue shows clear correlation of its response with human perception for various substances. This correlation can be established by appropriate pattern recognition techniques for

both qualitative and quantitative analysis of the test samples. The sensor array of ET works on liquid samples where the sensors respond on the whole for the different ingredients of the solution but not to a specific constituent of the solution, i.e., the responses of the sensors are non-specific [1]. So, depending on the presence of different ions and compounds, the collective response of the ET sensors varies from solution to solution.

Fig. 1. Typical electronic tongue-based analysis system: (a) training phase and (b) testing phase.

The use of electronic tongue to analyze any substance has two phases- i) training phase and ii) testing phase, as revealed in Fig. 1. In the training phase, as shown in Fig. 1(a), a classifier is trained to develop a model that establishes the correlation between the patterns extracted from the training samples and the corresponding targets (taste or quality) provided by the human test panels. In the testing phase, as shown in Fig. 1(b), an unknown sample is examined by the trained classifier model using the same features extracted from

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the response of ET. The performance of a typical ET system for a particular application depends on the quality of the extracted features from the response of the ET and the classifier model developed for recognition.

An electronic tongue system may offer many advantages such as: (a) more objectivity compared to human sensory panel, (b) high repeatability, (c) quick measurement, (d) requires small sample volume, (e) small size of sensors, (f) ease of operation by inexpert personnel and (g) usability to fully automatic long-term routine application. But at present there are no such commercially available systems which can provide all the above listed benefits. As a result more research work is required to obtain the above benefits from the ET methodology and make it more suitable for industrial use.

A. Literature Review

The electronic tongue system available in literature can be categorized based on the measurement techniques of their responses, such as potentiometry [4], voltammetry [5], and amperometry [6], etc. These measurement techniques have been successfully applied for the quality evaluation of food products like milk [7], water [8] and fruit juice [9], etc. A significant work was done by Ivarsson et al. [5] for the classification of black tea by using a voltammetric electronic tongue. Fluorometry based ET has been established in [10] for determining taste levels of astringency umami in tea infusions. A potentiometric ET has been used in [2] to determine the taste of Korean green tea. Use of ET was reported in [11] to estimate the concentrations of chemical components in drinking water.

Dynamic response corresponding to each sensor of the ET system may consist of large number of measured values depending on the measuring principle. As a result, the ET dataset is usually too large and complex to interpret. Consequently, different types of analysis techniques are required for efficient interpretation of the data. For this purpose it is necessary to extract characteristic features from the signals prior to classification. In the literature, some feature extraction methods are proposed from the transient response of electronic nose [12]. A new strategy to extract features from the response of a thermally modulated semiconductor sensor was proposed by Ding et al. [13] for gas identification. In [14], the authors have proposed principal component analysis (PCA) with Wilks distribution to predict the drinks by an array of gas sensors. But the problem is how many principal components (PCs) should be taken in the analysis, as we know that excessive PCs will contain too much noise and insufficient PCs will miss some important features [15]. Recently, Cetó et al. [16] employed a windowed slicing integral (WSI) method to divide the voltammogram into a number of sections and area under each section was used to capture the voltammetric waveform characteristic for assessment of individual polyphenol content in beer. Besides these, there are some other feature extraction methods in literature that use phase space of the sensor response curve, such as extracting phase space integral (PSI) [17] and phase space entire (PSE) [18]. Discrete wavelet transform (DWT)

based data compression and PCA techniques are reported in [19], [20] for electronic tongue based black tea quality prediction where all the signal responses are concatenated to make one large signal and thereby compressed using DWT [21]-[25], to represent the entire signal.

B. Contribution to This Work

All the previous techniques presented in literature considered the ET response as a one-dimensional signal by concatenating the individual responses of the sensors. As a result the signal loses the information of occurrences of diverse frequency components from different sensors. In order to overcome this drawback, we have considered the response of the voltammetric ET as a multidimensional-signal in this research work. To extract features from the transient response of each electrode of the sensor array in ET an overlapping moving window is used to divide the multidimensional signal into a number of signals of short duration. Then DWT of each of these signals under a window is computed to find out the signal energy in different frequency band. These energy values are taken as the patterns of the ET response under a window. In order to test a sample, the response of the ET signal is similarly divided into a number of signals and the output type of each of these signals are determined by the trained classifier. Finally, the class label of the sample is determined by the maximum vote obtained in favor of a particular class.

In addition, this work shows the effect of the window size on the classification performance. This effect is also observed for three different wavelets, namely haar, bior and db8. The performance of the proposed feature set has been assessed by two different kernel classifiers namely, multiclass support vector machine (SVM) [26]-[29], and recently developed vector valued regularized kernel function approximation (VVRKFA) [30]-[32], technique of multiclass data classification. High prediction accuracy of both the classifiers indicates the effectiveness of the proposed technique of feature extraction and prediction of black tea quality using ET signal.

C. Organization of the Paper

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: In section II the experimentation process is described. The details of the proposed feature extraction and prediction techniques are elaborated in section III. Experimental results and analysis are provided in the section IV. Finally, section V concludes the paper.

II. EXPERIMENTATION

A. Electronic Tongue System

The Electronic Tongue (ET) based on pulse voltammetric method has been reported by the authors in [3]. The ET consists of an array of five different noble metal type working electrodes, made up of gold, palladium, platinum, iridium and rhodium; an Ag/AgCl reference electrode (saturated KCl, Gamry Instruments Inc., USA) and a platinum counter electrode (PH Ionics, India). The ET system has four different modules as shown by the functional block diagram in fig. 2.

These are 1) an array of electrodes; 2) a PC based signal generation unit along with a software controlled amplifier, level shifter and switching circuit; 3) PC-based data acquisition; and 4) taste characterization software. LabVIEW® based virtual instrumentation system (VIS) has been used for signal generation and data acquisition by using USB 6008 of National Instruments. The data acquisition card generates/acquires the voltage points at a frequency of 100 Hz. The VIS generates a pulse waveform with amplitude varying from 0 to 500mV in small steps specified by the user and then the pulse waveform is amplified by two times and shifted by a negative voltage of 200mV by an amplifier and a level shifter respectively. Thus, a signal varying—from -0.2 to +0.8 V is applied to the tea samples through one of the five working electrodes once at a time where the electrodes are selected sequentially by using a switching circuit controlled by the digital outputs from the data acquisition card.

Fig. 2. Functional block diagram of the electronic tongue system.

In this work three types of voltammetric pulses, e.g. large amplitude pulse voltammetry (LAPV), small amplitude pulse voltammetry (SAPV) and STAIRCASE are applied. For example, in case of the LAPV waveform, 21 voltage levels constituted by the decreasing voltages ranging from 0.8 to -0.2 volt and separated by equal width zero volts are applied to the test sample. Each voltage level is maintained for approximately 330 ms. Corresponding to each applied voltage point, a current response is recorded. The response waveform is constituted by the sequence of responses from each electrode collected sequentially. The time required for measuring the current responses sequentially from 5 electrodes is 34.7 s. The dynamics of the actual response signal is shown in Fig. 3 for LAPV. But in this work we have considered the individual responses collectively as if they were generated from multi-sensors simultaneously by the application of different types of pulses as shown in Fig. 4. In case of LAPV and SAPV, 694 data points are collected from each electrode and hence the complete response for five electrodes consists of $5 \times 694 = 3470$ measurement points for a single run. The actual dimension of each measurement data is thus 1×3470 and in this application it is used as multi-signal constituting 5×694 data points. Similarly, for STAIRCASE waveform $5 \times 760 = 3800$ measurement points were collected and thus the actual dimension of each measured data in this case is 1×3800 whereas in multi-signal representation it is 5×760 data points.

B. Sample Preparation

The test samples are prepared by pouring the boiled 150ml of distilled water over 750 mg of dry tea sample and then the

solution is brewed for 5 minutes. Now the solution is passed through a filter paper to separate the tea leaves. The obtained liquor is then allowed to cool at room temperature for 20 minutes and is ready for measurement. The electrodes are rinsed with distilled water after each measurement.

Fig. 3 Response of the e-tongue as recorded by the system for LAPV.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Fig. 4. Typical multisensor response of electronic tongue using (a) SAPV (b) LAPV and (c) STAIRCASE method.

III. PROPOSED METHOD OF FEATURE EXTRACTION

A. Feature Extraction

In a multi-sensor system, a measurement is characterized by a large number of measured values and this makes the task of black tea quality evaluation a challenging one by using the voltammetric electronic tongue. One of the vital tasks of any pattern recognition-based system is the extraction of relevant features. Considering this we have explored a set of features that can address this problem. In order to reduce the dimensionality of the data and to explore its dynamics we have proposed a sliding window-based feature extraction from

the multi-sensor signal using discrete wavelet transform (DWT). As DWT provides a time-scale (frequency) representation [23]-[25], [33] of a signal, it can provide a deep look within the transient response of the sensors by analyzing the energy associated with different frequency bands present in the small segments of ET response. The wavelet energy reflects the degree of similarity between different parts of the signal. This is the key intuition of the proposed technique in this problem.

To localize the presence of different frequency bands in the measured ET signal, we have considered a sliding window containing W_s (say) number of measured samples. In order to compromise between the computational complexity and consistency in characteristics among the adjacent windowed signals we have chosen an overlap of 50% between the successive windows. This means that the window moves forward by $W_s / 2$ no of samples. The choice of the width of the window depends on the characteristics of the signal. The size of the window should be extended to a sufficient amount to put up the relatively slow frequencies of the signal. On the other hand it should be small enough to be responsive to transient changes in the signal. Due to this reason we have tried to find out suitable window size for this application by conducting the experiment with different window size, e.g., 32, 64, 128 and 256. It is observed that for small window size, e.g., 32 and 64, the energy of the detail coefficients after 3rd level of decomposition becomes very small. For higher window size it may have some significant value. But to have uniformity in feature length and ease of computation we have chosen three levels of decomposition of DWT for different types of window size.

In order to extract features the discrete signals within each window (i.e., $5 \times W_s$ number of samples) experience DWT with the help of filter bank [23]-[25]. The filter bank decomposes each individual signals separately into two lower scales components. In the succeeding iteration, the approximation coefficients are again passed through the filter banks to generate the detail ($d_j(n)$) and approximate coefficients ($a_j(n)$) in next scale [23-25], where j indicates the scale and n indicates the number of samples in that scale. In this fashion, we have decomposed the input samples under each window into three different scales and extracted the detail coefficients ($d_j(n)$). The feature vector is formed by considering the energy of the signal at different scales or frequency band. This can be computed by the squared 2-norm $\|\bullet\|^2$ of the detail coefficients d_j at each level for each individual signal within one window, i.e.,

$$f_i = \left[\|d_1(n)\|^2 \ \|d_2(n)\|^2 \ \|d_3(n)\|^2 \right]_{j=1,2,3}^T. \quad (1)$$

For each individual signal, f_i consists of energy of three frequency bands for the i th sensor's output. Thus, the final feature vector f_r is formed by concatenating the energy values

of all ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) the sensor's output for the r th position of the window $W_s^{(r)}$, i.e., $f_r = [f_1 \ f_2 \ \dots \ f_5]^T$, which is a 15-dimensional feature vector. This procedure of feature extraction is depicted by the Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Proposed window-based feature extraction method for ET signal.

B. Training Data Formation

In any ET measurement system if there are M number of measured samples then we can construct approximately $r = M / (W_s / 2) - 1$ number of window for each sample S_i neglecting few end samples if anything there. Each such signal window is characterized by a 15×1 feature vector and each of them assigned a class label j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, L$) if the sample belongs to class j and value of L is 4 here for this problem. For example, in LAPV method there are 694 number of measurement points in our experiment. If we consider a window of size 32 the number of window for one sample will be $r = 694 / (32 / 2) - 1 \hat{=} 42$. So, if we have N no. of samples the size of the training data matrix becomes $(N \times 42) \times 15$. To choose the mother wavelet that performs best on the obtained data, six different mother wavelets, namely haar, bior3.5, db8, db2, symlet, and coiflet are chosen initially in our work. The response of the e-tongue is decomposed by each individual wavelet up to three levels. The mean square error between the original and the reconstructed signal from the obtained approximation and detail coefficients was used as the parameter to select the mother wavelets. It is observed that haar, bior3.5 and db8 provide the lowest mean square error and hence we have considered them in this work. For each measurement system we frame different training sets considering different types of wavelets.

C. Testing of a Sample

In order to test an unknown sample S_i , it is first windowed and then feature f_r is extracted from each window position $W_s^{(r)}$ on the signal in a similar manner as the training data are prepared. The class labels of each individual test feature f_r are determined by the trained classifier model. Each test feature cast a vote $v^{(r)}$ in favor of a class j ($j = 1, 2, \dots, L$), for a L -class classification problem. Finally, the grade of a tea sample S_i is determined by the maximum number of vote in favor of a particular class, i.e.,

$$\text{class}(S_i) = \arg \max_{j=1}^L (V(j)), \quad (2)$$

where $V(j)$ is the number of vote in favor of class j .

IV. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

A. Sample Collection and Data Description

In this work, experimentation with ET has been performed with several tea samples collected from Kanan Devan Hill Plantation of southern India along with the tea tasters' score. The scores are assigned against the 'strength' of the liquor without milk and based on the combined perception of taste, briskness and astringency of the tea samples in the range 5 to 8. The number of samples in four different categories and in different voltammetric measurement techniques are listed in Table

TABLE I
NUMBER OF SAMPLES IN DIFFERENT CLASSES (GRADES) FOR THREE
TYPES OF ET SIGNALS

Class (Grade)	LAPV	SAPV	STAIRCASE
5	25	25	25
6	20	25	15
7	25	23	25
8	25	25	25
Total samples	95	98	90

I.

B. Experimental Procedure

We have evaluated the performances of multi-class OVO-SVM [28] and VVRKFA classifiers [30] on the proposed feature set by using both polynomial and Gaussian kernel. For the implementation of OVO-SVM we have used LIBSVM Toolbox [34] and VVRKFA is implemented in MATLAB as explained in [31]. The optimal value of the regularization parameter C for SVM and VVRKFA is selected from the set of values $\{2^i \mid i = -5, -4, \dots, 15\}$ and $\{10^i \mid i = -6, -5, \dots, -1\}$, respectively. The optimal values of Gaussian kernel parameter γ and the degree of polynomial kernel d of both the classifiers are selected from the set $\{2^i \mid i = -8, -7, \dots, 8\}$ and $\{2, 3, 4, 5, 6\}$, respectively. The optimal parameter set is selected by the performance of a classifier on a tuning set comprising of 20% of training data while the remaining 80% training data are used to train the classifier [35]. Finally, we have evaluated the performance of a classifier using the full

data set with the selected optimal parameters by 10-fold cross validation (CV) method [35]. Each training feature is normalized in the range [0 1]. In order to calculate the accuracy, random permutations of the data points are performed before proceeding to the tests. We have observed the performance of the feature sets extracted by using three different wavelets for each data sets. In all the experiments we have observed the effect of variation of window size on the performance of classifiers. The best accuracy result in each Table is made bold.

C. Experimental Results

In this section we have provided the experimental results separately for three different voltammetric data sets as shown in Table I. For each data set we have observed the performance of the proposed technique for different window length and for three different types of wavelets. From Table II it is observed that in case of SAPV data the haar wavelet features with window size 64 has the best performance by using OVO-SVM classifier. Haar features with window size 32 perform almost equally to that of using window size 64 by SVM classifier. Further, OVO-SVM performs better than VVRKFA in most of the cases. The important fact observed from Table II is that performance degrades with the increase of the window size.

TABLE II
10-FOLD CV PERFORMANCE ON SAPV-BASED DATA SET

Window Size	Wavelet type	Classifier type	% testing accuracy (std.) with Gaussian kernel	% testing accuracy (std.) with polynomial kernel
32	haar	OVO SVM	98.89 (3.33)	84.78 (11.96)
		VVRKFA	95.00 (8.06)	89.89 (11.84)
	db8	OVO SVM	95.89 (5.04)	76.56 (17.43)
		VVRKFA	87.78 (10.74)	84.78 (9.11)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	89.89 (10.01)	79.44 (13.63)
		VVRKFA	88.78 (6.98)	76.56 (9.96)
64	haar	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	94.89 (6.80)
		VVRKFA	96.00 (9.17)	91.89 (8.75)
	db8	OVO SVM	97.00 (4.58)	93.89 (6.71)
		VVRKFA	94.00 (8.00)	91.89 (7.59)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	94.00 (8.00)	90.89 (7.02)
		VVRKFA	91.89 (11.69)	89.78 (6.34)
128	haar	OVO SVM	96.89 (4.76)	98.00 (4.00)
		VVRKFA	96.00 (4.90)	89.78 (10.24)
	db8	OVO SVM	91.78 (10.09)	92.00 (8.72)
		VVRKFA	94.89 (6.80)	90.89 (10.46)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	94.00 (6.63)	90.78 (5.44)
		VVRKFA	93.00 (10.05)	92.89 (10.09)
256	haar	OVO SVM	96.00 (9.17)	93.78 (5.10)
		VVRKFA	96.78 (4.93)	92.67 (8.24)
	db8	OVO SVM	93.00 (10.05)	90.89 (10.45)
		VVRKFA	94.78 (5.24)	89.00 (12.21)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	88.89 (9.43)	87.00 (13.45)
		VVRKFA	87.78 (10.00)	88.67 (10.13)

On the other hand, Table III shows that LAPV data are highly and equally classifiable by the feature sets derived by using haar, db8 and bior3.5 wavelets with different window size. Among them both OVO-SVM and VVRKFA give 99.0% accuracy in all the cases with window size 64 and Gaussian kernel. Table IV shows that staircase data are also highly

classifiable by using haar or bior3.5 wavelets with window size 64 or 128. In the three different data sets Gaussian kernel, in general, performs better than polynomial kernel. In view of all these results it may be conclude that haar features with window size 64 will be suitable for the black tea quality

TABLE III
10-FOLD CV PERFORMANCE ON LAPV-BASED DATA SET

Window Size	Wavelet type	Classifier type	% testing accuracy (std.) with Gaussian kernel	% testing accuracy (std.) with polynomial kernel
32	haar	OVO SVM	98.89 (3.33)	95.89(6.74)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	99.00(3.00)
	db8	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	99.00(3.00)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	99.00 (3.00)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	97.89 (4.23)	94.78 (8.49)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	99.00 (3.00)
64	haar	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	97.78 (6.67)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	98.89 (3.33)
	db8	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	99.00 (3.00)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.33)	97.89 (4.23)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	90.78 (9.47)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	97.00 (6.40)
128	haar	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	95.67 (7.28)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	96.89 (6.53)
	db8	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	97.89 (4.23)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	99.00 (3.00)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	90.44 (8.93)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	96.89 (4.76)
256	haar	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	95.89 (5.04)
		VVRKFA	97.89 (4.29)	96.78 (7.00)
	db8	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	96.67 (5.09)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	99.00 (3.00)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	95.78 (7.18)	92.56 (9.66)
		VVRKFA	95.89 (6.74)	89.44 (8.06)

Fig. 6. Bar plot of feature values extracted by using a window of size 64 from LAPV data set for four categories of tea grades; (a) grade five, (b) grade six, (c) grade seven and (d) grade eight.

TABLE IV
10-FOLD CV PERFORMANCE ON STAIRCASE DATA SET

Window Size	Wavelet type	Classifier type	% testing accuracy (std.) with Gaussian kernel	% testing accuracy (std.) with polynomial kernel
32	haar	OVO SVM	96.67 (7.11)	84.44 (12.37)
		VVRKFA	95.56 (5.44)	95.56 (5.44)
	db8	OVO SVM	94.44 (7.45)	83.33 (16.67)
		VVRKFA	96.67 (5.09)	94.44 (5.56)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	84.44 (12.37)	83.33 (11.39)
		VVRKFA	96.67 (5.09)	94.44 (7.45)
64	haar	OVO SVM	98.89 (3.33)	91.11 (9.69)
		VVRKFA	97.78 (4.44)	97.78 (4.44)
	db8	OVO SVM	97.78 (4.44)	95.56 (7.37)
		VVRKFA	97.78 (4.44)	96.67 (5.09)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	97.78 (4.44)	91.11 (10.89)
		VVRKFA	99.00 (3.00)	97.78 (6.67)
128	haar	OVO SVM	99.00 (3.00)	97.78 (4.44)
		VVRKFA	97.78 (4.44)	97.78 (4.44)
	db8	OVO SVM	97.78 (6.67)	97.78 (4.44)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	97.78 (4.44)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	96.67 (5.09)	98.89 (3.33)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	97.78 (4.44)
256	haar	OVO SVM	96.67 (5.09)	96.67 (5.09)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	96.67 (5.09)
	db8	OVO SVM	98.89 (3.33)	98.89 (3.33)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	94.44 (7.45)
	bior3.5	OVO SVM	97.78 (4.44)	97.78 (4.44)
		VVRKFA	98.89 (3.33)	96.67 (5.09)

prediction using ET signal. The poor performance of the large window may be explained by the fact that the features extracted from these window fail to preserve the information pertaining to the spatial location of different fine details, so it cannot efficiently characterize the ET signals.

The excellent performance of the proposed feature set may be explained with the help of the bar plots as shown in the Fig. 6. This shows the variation of haar feature values extracted from the response of LAPV ET signal by using a window of size 64 for four different grades of tea samples. The Fig. 6 clearly shows dissimilar distribution profile of energy in different frequency bands for four different types of tea samples. As a result the proposed feature set is able to offer high classification accuracy on this problem.

V. CONCLUSION

In this work we have proposed a new feature extraction and classification technique of electronic tongue signal. The window-based wavelet feature extraction and classification by maximum voting method show very promising in tea quality prediction using different types of electronic tongue signal measurement. We have studied performance of three different types of wavelets. The results of tables II-IV proved that haar features with window size 64 will be suitable for the black tea quality prediction using ET signal. Other wavelets as well as different classification techniques can also be tested in this framework. In addition, performance of different types of features using different signal transformation techniques, such as discrete cosine transform (DCT), singular value decomposition (SVD), etc., may be evaluated in the same way.

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